

Do system navigation programs linking primary care with community-based health and social services improve user and healthcare system outcomes compared to usual care? A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

**21 Studies
Included**

**Primarily from North
America and Europe**

**Participants' average
age = 67 years**

Types of System Navigation Interventions

Lay person within primary care

Trained non-professionals

Health professional model

Health professional (e.g., social worker, nurse)

Team based model

Lay person(s) & health professional(s)
OR teams of health professionals

Self-navigation with lay support

Personalized list of local resources
with lay support available

Intervention Outcomes

Health and social service use

e.g., Primary care,
hospital,
emergency room visits

Patient level outcomes

e.g., Quality of life and
mental health, social
participation,
health behaviour, behaviour
change

Patient and caregiver experiences

e.g., Quality of care

Cost effectiveness

Producing good
results without costing
a lot of money

Caregiver Health

e.g., Strain,
mental health

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW RESULTS:

Type of system navigation interventions and impacts on outcomes

		Lay person within primary care (n=10)	Health professional model (n=4)	Team based model (n=6)	Self-navigation with lay support (n=1)
	<p>↑ Improvement</p> <p>↔ No impact/unclear</p> <p>n/a Not measured</p>				
Health and social service use		↔	↔	↑	n/a
Patient level outcomes		↔	↔	↔	↔
Patient and caregiver experiences		↑	↑	↔	n/a
Caregiver Health		n/a	↔	n/a	n/a
Cost effectiveness		↑*	n/a	n/a	n/a

* Potential benefits but insufficient data

Key Points

A team-based approach to system navigation may be effective at improving health and social service utilization.

Lay or health professional models may support improvement in patient experience outcomes e.g., quality of care.

The ideal model of system navigation remains unclear and further research is warranted.

CITATION: Ganann, R., Teggart, K., Neil-Sztramko, S.E., Nadarajah, A., Wang A., Carter, N., Adams, J., Jain, K., Petrie, P., Sheik, A., MacNeil, M., Ling., E. (2022). Do System Navigation Programs Linking Primary Care with Community-Based Health and Social Services Improve User and Healthcare System Outcomes Compared to Usual Care? A Systematic Review. Infographic.

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